

ELECTRIC DRIVE LCA & LCC METHODOLOGY FOR ENGINEERING SERVICES

Politecnico di Torino

EM-TECH

Holistic and robust evaluation of electric drive sustainability

Support circular economy in e-mobility

Quantified benefits of recycling strategies

CHALLENGES AND SOLUTION:

Current sustainability assessments in e-mobility often overlook drivetrain life cycle costs (LCC) and environmental impacts (LCA). Our research fills this gap by developing a combined LCA and LCC methodology, applied to two powertrain solutions mounting different permanent magnet synchronous motors: in-wheel motor (IWM) and on-board motor (OBM). Both production and use phases were analyzed, alongside scenarios for end-of-life management.

human toxicity, particulate matter, marine eutrophication, freshwater ecotoxicity, and mineral resource use. These impacts are driven by copper electrorefining and neodymium oxide refining. For the OBM, production dominates most impact categories, highlighting the importance of product-specific analysis.

Electricity mix strongly affects results: using offshore wind reduces IWM GHG emissions by 75% and OBM by 47% against the average EU electricity mix. In contrast, coal-based electricity increases IWM emissions by 163% and OBM by 102%.

Recycling further reduces impacts, demonstrating the importance of eco-design for dismantling, material separation, and circularity. Structural design choices, material combinations (e.g., copper and aluminum), and assembly methods directly influence dismantling feasibility and material separation. These insights encourage design for dismantling approaches that enable higher recycling efficiency and permanent magnet recovery, foster circular supply chains, and ultimately reduce the environmental footprint of electric mobility.

We aim to extend this methodology to additional motor types, integrate eco-design recommendations into engineering workflows, and collaborate with industry partners to support sustainable drivetrain innovation.

Figure 1: LCA (climate change) and LCC results of two different drivetrains, one mounting two IWMs on the rear axle of a JAC iEV7 (left-hand side) and the other mounting a radial flux OBM on a Volkswagen ID3 (right-hand side).

IMPACT & NEXT STEPS:

For the IWM, the use phase dominates greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions due to drivetrain losses, vehicle energy consumption, and electricity generation. Production, however, is the main driver for

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